

Evaluating Students Feedback Towards Teachers Performance on E-learning

Sarbast H. Ali, Sardar Omar Salih, Arman Ismael Mohammed & Omer Mohammed Salih Hassan

Abstract:

Internet use in the Kurdistan region of Iraq has grown dramatically and has become an essential element of our daily lives, with hundred ISPs on hand and constantly increasing number of users by using e-learning platforms. The need for feedback is deeply linked to student participation and peer evaluation. It is also an issue of evaluation quality; how many feedbacks is made available, how they are given to students, how they are accepted by students, and to how much they are integrated into future instruction and learning. In this paper, three instruments, documentation, interviews and questionnaires were carried out to collect the data. Documentation was used to know the experiences of the students during classroom teaching and learning. The data were collected from the system application on our website. The data were called documentation. A survey is conducted comparing the feedback received from students on e-learning courses at the Duhok Polytechnic University (DPU), with the results of analyzed 100 teachers' e-learning courses in the Covid-19 period in 2020. Eighteen questions have been asked to 7709 students in 14 technical faculties (6 colleges and 8 institutes) at DPU. The students' responses were classified to the questions related to teachers' experiences on preparing courses, students' interactions, using available e-learning tools and methods. A review has been made on (100) teachers' courses in the Moodle platform as LMS (learning management systems) to reveal their course preparation, experiences on using available technologies. Our results showed 34.92% of participant students satisfied with e-learning, this means that 65.08% of students preferred face-to-face learning (in class), regarding the trustiness of feedback, reviewed courses and students' responses which were significantly mismatched. This means that student feedback is not entirely reliable in the learning process.

Keywords: *E-learning, feedback, questionnaires, teacher experiences, survey.*

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About Author (s)

Sarbast H. Ali (corresponding author), Information Technology Department, Duhok Polytechnic University (DPU), Duhok, Iraq. Email: sarbast.ali@dpu.edu.krd

Sardar Omar Salih, Information Technology Department, Duhok Technical Institute, Duhok Polytechnic University (DPU), Duhok, Iraq.

Arman Ismael Mohammed, Information Technology Department, Duhok Polytechnic University (DPU), Duhok, Iraq.

Omer Mohammed Salih Hassan, Information Technology Department, Duhok Polytechnic University (DPU), Duhok, Iraq.

1. Introduction

The usability of technology has been growing dramatically in the last decade in the Kurdistan Region (Rashid et al., 2016). Therefore, the universities in the region started to benefit from this development. In 2015, the National University Ranking (NUR) for public and private universities in Kurdistan region announced by the Ministry of Higher Education (MHE-KRG), and one of the criteria of this ranking is an E-Systems which includes the university website, e-learning, student feedback system and alumni system (Esmail Kh et al., 2018). Therefore, several higher education universities began to develop such systems related to the students in order to meet the NUR ranking criteria. The DPU like many other universities started to apply Moodle e-learning platform system in their colleges and institutions in the academic year 2017-2018. Also, the DPU started to develop several systems related to the teaching and learning and one of them was a student feedback system. The feedback is one of the strongest impacts on the learning process and performance, but this can be either positive or negative (Hattie et al., 2007). According to (Spencer et al., 2002), the feedback collection from students is regarded one of the most sensitive, divisive and political issues in education. They confirmed that the students feedback process is important for teachers, managers and students. Each of them benefits from it in different ways. Teachers could use feedback to improve their teaching. The managers are using information in the process of promoting teachers while students are using feedback as a guide for selecting modules and courses. However, occasionally the insufficient information about the purpose of collecting feedback could lead to an increase in the percent of cynicism among students and staff. Also, if the announced purpose is far from the reality, this would lead to the students always believing that their feedback would never improve the teaching process. (Chen et al., 2003). In contrast, the aim of collecting feedback from students is to develop the quality of the teaching. This is such a prove to the students that the teaching administration is respond to their feedback. Unfortunately, the responsible department of the feedback process is fails to achieve this aim. For example, in the University of Tasmania which is located in Australia, after 3 or 4 years of collecting students feedback from 25 departments, it was found that there are no changes in the quality of teaching (Kember et al., 2002). The aim of this research is to compare students' feedback with the reviewed teachers' courses which will reveal teachers' experiences on e-learning and students feedback reliability for making decisions. The first method used is a questionnaire by asking students 18 questions related to e-learning. The second method, 100 teachers' online courses have been analyzed according to their aspect that is included in the questionnaire. The objective of the present study is to gain a clear view how teachers respond to critical feedback. Critical mentor feedback is interpreted by a mentor in post-observation supervision sessions during teaching and as information which states or questions whether there is a need to change aspects of performance or understanding. (Bjørndal, 2020)

2. Literature review

Feedback from students is a rich and valuable source for both formative and summative information. Therefore, most institutions collect their students' feedback in many different ways. The assessment of students' teaching provides many decision makers in the higher education topic potential benefits in the right way. The knowledge will be used to design and manage curricula, development of teaching and thus complete quality cycles through proper evaluation and interpretation (Kassim et al., 2017). In the context where knowledge grows rapidly and technology and work processes rapidly change, for over two decades researchers, educator leaders, policymakers and business leaders have highlighted the need to support "21st century" skills. These skills include critical thinking and solving problems, the ability to find, analyze, synthesize and apply knowledge to emerging situations; the ability to inter-

personal skills that enable people to work with others and to engage effectively with intercultural contexts; the ability to manage their own work and to manage complex projects (Darling-hammond et al., 2019). Learning and student learning is the teacher's aim, but teachers can learn how to better teach by students. Virtually every post-secondary school in the United States uses a teaching method or course assessment. The assessment of teaching can come from many sources such as (self-assessment, co-assessment and study techniques) as well as teaching and course assessments (Dechesne, 2019). However, as they mature in their educational careers, students interpret feedback in several ways. In general, students with little previous learning knowledge tend to regard feedback as explicit reactions to, feedback is considered to be the primary element in formative evaluations and one of the most important factors for learning, this position is emphasized more and more in policy papers that teachers trust and are expected to become integrated into education institutions' cultures (Wenjua et al., 2019). Determined differing impacts of education policy on the positioning and performance of teachers, claiming that policy stories "form what they mean to be a teacher, learner and educated" differentiate the imperative and urgent policy of education, its position of teachers as professionals and differential power relations between policy makers in general, governmental or other educational institutions and policy makers in general, and schools and teachers in classrooms. Important reforms contain 'mainly inactive,' 'reactive' and 'technical' characters, with a strategy that determine and restrict behavior and effectiveness.(Vattøy, 2020). Students react to their feedback on their previous experience and their own individual characteristics in different ways, within specific disciplines, curriculums and contextual environments. In our section, we look at how students understand and appreciate feedback processes in developing capacity for the making of academic evaluations. We look at how students handle affective factors (Carless et al., 2018a). Teachers see their feedback emotionally very differently. Some people welcome it, others are less satisfied. In a fairly earlier study, report reduced job satisfaction and morale and, following regular student feedback, a more negative view of university administration, whereas in a much newer study, the attitude towards evaluations is moderately positive demonstrate that most of the educators concentrate too much on negative feedback whereas others concentrate mostly on positive feedback, and also that the assessment of feedback may not always be sensible. Educators also submit an impression of anxiety and depression about student assessments while unusual are insulting comments (Flodén et al., 2016). Feedback from students can be described the use of qualitative methods to collect feedback from student on their understanding of teaching, educator efficiency and educational quality. Use student feedback for their satisfaction and perceptions of learnings gains at a subject's end to typically serve as the most common way of collecting feedback (Mandouit et al., 2018).

3. Methodology

Students answered to the questionnaire to give their opinion about the online learning in the COVID-19 era in academic year 2019-2020. The students' answers calculated to gain the overall results in each department separately. Then, 100 teachers' online courses have been analyzed to make a comparison with the students' feedback to evaluate teachers' performance.

3.1. Data Collection and Classification

The questionnaire consists of 18 questions, has been prepared by the Ministry of Higher Education in Kurdistan Region (MHE-KRG). The questions cover all the aspects in the e-learning after the classification process on it, such as teachers' preparation (course organization), course contents, learning outcoming and (methods) techniques to involve students in the course. The following 'Table 1' show prepared questions for the students and its classification.

Table 1: Questionnaires questions and its classification

#	Question	Question classification
1.	Online learning materials were accessible	Uploaded resources
2.	Tools and technology were easy to use and accessible for all	Availability of e-learning
3.	The contents of the course were useful and interesting	Course organized
4.	The lecture was structured and well organized	Course organized
5.	The audio and visual connections were good	Uploaded resources
6.	The course clearly explained what you were expected to learn from the course (i.e. give learning objectives)	Student satisfaction on E-learning
7.	The course was very effective at helping us reach those learning objectives	Course organized
8.	All the images and texts in the course were clearly visible	Course organized
9.	Sounds in the course were clearly audible	Uploaded resources
10.	The information in the course was easily understandable	Course organized
11.	Further guidance was offered where information was complex	Course organized
12.	Rate the availability of the instructor via email or online discussion	Interaction Method
13.	The content adequately explained the knowledge, skills, and concepts it presented	Interaction Method
14.	The download time for the course pages was satisfied	Experiences on uploaded
15.	The course instructor was accessible to answer questions or give feedback	Interaction Method
16.	I was satisfied with the online interaction I had with the instructor	Interaction Method
17.	I was satisfied with the amount of online interaction I had with other students in this course	Students interaction with each other's
18.	Overall, I was satisfied with the course	Student satisfaction on E-learning

4. Student's feedback analysis and evaluation

The students have five options to answer each question. The options are 'Very Dissatisfied', 'Dissatisfied', 'Less Satisfied', 'Satisfied' or 'Very Satisfied' as shown in the 'Table 2' below. Each of these choices have its numeric values ranging from 1-5 for calculating feedback's results. The following 'Table 2' shows numerical values to each choice.

Table 2: Student answer options

Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Less Satisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
1	2	3	4	5
Dissatisfied		Satisfied		

The feedback system is a web-based application which is developed in a way to collect students' responses as a number, and calculated in order to generate the final result with satisfaction or dissatisfaction of each question separately. Below is a case showing how the

feedback system calculates the results for 'Department X' with three students. Tables 3, 4 and 5 show the responses for three students. **Department X feedback results from students.**

Table 3: Student 1 answers

Q*	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1								
R*	2	4	1	5	2	1	5	3	2	2	1	5	2	4	4	5	3	2

Table 4: Student 2 answers

Q*	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1								
R*	5	4	4	1	3	2	5	3	1	4	5	2	4	5	5	3	1	1

Table 5: Student 3 answers

Q*	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1								
R*	3	4	4	2	3	2	5	3	1	4	5	2	4	5	5	3	1	1

Q* = Question., R* = Result.

The feedback system collects the students' responses as in the above tables to find the number of 'Satisfied' or 'Dissatisfied' students with each question. As it appeared in 'Table 2', the 'Satisfied' students are those who answered 3, 4 or 5 to each question. In contrast, the 'Dissatisfied' students are those who answered 1 or 2.

Based on the above, in the 'Department X', the first question response is: 2 students are satisfied (SAT) and 1 is not satisfied (DSAT) while the second question response is: all students are satisfied (SAT) and no one is dissatisfied (DSAT). The same process has been applied to all questions. Table 6 shows the number of students who Satisfied and Dissatisfied to each question in the 'Department X'.

Table 6: Department x responses analyzed

*Q	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1								
*S#1	2	4	1	5	2	1	5	3	2	2	1	5	2	4	4	5	3	2
*S#2	5	4	4	1	3	2	5	3	1	4	5	2	4	5	5	3	1	1
*S#3	3	4	4	2	3	2	5	3	1	4	5	2	4	5	5	3	1	1
*SAT	2	3	2	1	2	0	3	3	0	2	2	1	2	3	3	3	1	0
*DSAT	1	0	1	2	1	3	0	0	3	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	2	3

*Q: Question., *S: Student., *SAT: Satisfied., *DSAT: Dissatisfied.

As calculated above in the feedback system, DPU students' responses were analyzed, as a result of the percentage of satisfied students to each question along with its category as concluded in the following chart. Noting, the highest number of the students' satisfaction were on question number 12 and 15 which are classified as 'interaction methods' in the questionnaire table above. Whereas the lowest rates were on questions classified as a 'course organization' in number 7 and 10.

Fig.1. Student satisfied rate for each question

The last question in the questionnaire is about students' conviction on e-learning, over all, 34.92% of the students prefer blended learning over in class learning. By looking at the above chart (Fig. 1), it can be noticed that the highest and lowest satisfaction rate was located between 33.88%- 49.31%. In the following chart (Fig. 2), the average of the students' satisfaction rate was recorded for each category of questions and observed that the highest percent was on the questions which are related to the 'interaction methods' while the lowest was related to the questions classified as 'availability of technologies and usability'. The other categories such as 'course organized', 'experiences on uploaded', 'student satisfaction on e-learning' and 'students' interaction with each other' are approximately equally with a rate of 37%.

Fig. 2. Average of satisfied on each group of questions

5. Teachers' Courses analysis and Evaluation

100 courses have been selected randomly from DPU colleges and institutions in the Moodle platform for evaluating teachers' preparations, teachers' experiences, course management (Course Setup), uploaded digital contents and communications methods to involve students in the e-learning course. Table 7 was prepared by our team to evaluate a teacher' preparations courses, 9 questions were answered with either satisfied or dissatisfied of each course. Then, calculating the percentage of satisfied and dissatisfied of each question individually in order to gain the full percent.

1. Table 7: Teachers' preparations evaluation

Course setup		Course contents			Interaction methods and student's evaluation			
Course organization	Instructions provided	Text-based Documents uploaded	Video uploaded	Audio uploaded	Quiz	Forum/chat	Assignments	online class link
*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST	*ST or *DST

*ST : Satisfied, *DST :Dissatisfied

According to the previous table (Table 7), courses were analyzed and results were shown in the chart below. It was noted that 74% of the courses were well-organized and students were instructed, in contrast, the rest percent which was 26% of courses were not clearly organized. In addition, most of the uploaded files in the Moodle platform were in a documents format such as PDF, Word Document, PowerPoint and Excel Sheet which were available in 98% of courses. The other contents such as videos and it's percent was 54% and the rest 7% of the files were audio, see the chart below (Fig. 4) for full percentages. Audio and chat/forum were the least e-learning methods used in the courses. For example, audios resources were found in 7 courses out of 100 and char/forum were in just 10 courses out of 100. Student interaction methods, quizzes and assignments were the highest techniques used by the teachers to evaluate students' learning outcomes. The other methods such as forum/chat and online meeting links were the lowest techniques used to involve students in the course. The following chart (Fig. 3) shows the teacher's experience in an e-learning process.

Fig. 3. E-learning methods overview in teachers' courses

The courses which were involved in this review were divided into four main disciplines: engineering, business administrations, information technology and health. By looking at the following chart (Fig. 4), 70-80% of courses were “well prepared” in all reviewed disciplines and 93% of the engineering courses provide instruction and recorded the highest percentage among the others. Almost all courses were uploaded resources in the text-based content. The IT and engineering courses were the highest departments that used video in their courses, and the lowest audio contents were found in the courses for all reviewed disciplines. The following chart (Fig. 4) shows e-learning methods for each discipline.

Fig. 4. E-learning courses' discipline overview

6. Assessment and Recommendations

The student responses were collected and analyzed, then compared with the results of reviewing courses in DPU colleges and institutes. The percentage of the students who prefer e-learning over traditional face-to-face is 34.92%. This means that most students were not satisfied with e-learning, as a result, the majority of the students' answers to each question were dissatisfied. In the questions related to course organization, 74% of courses which were reviewed by our team were 'Satisfied', whereas in students feedback, the average of questions on the course organized was recorded 37.92%. 98% of teachers' uploaded contents were in the text-based format while in the student responses to uploaded contents questions, the average responses are 42% of students agreed that content is “well uploaded”. Moreover, question number 5 that is related to the uploaded multimedia contents such as video and audio with 34% of students agreed to be used in their courses, however, in reviewed courses was 54%. In addition, 7% of teachers used videos and audios tools in their courses. In students' feedback, the questions that were related to the communication methods such as forums, chats and live classes were recorded as the highest preferred techniques of communication, in contrast, in the reviewed teachers' courses process, these techniques were least used to interact with the students. In the results of reviewing teacher courses, firstly, the questions related to 'Courses Setup' noted that most of the teachers were able to organize their courses at a rate of 74%. Then, in the questions related to the content of courses, the highest percent of courses' content

were in text-based format, then videos and audios, the audio was the least used in their courses. Finally, quizzes and assignments were the highest interaction methods found in the teachers' courses, however, the forum, chat and online methods were less used in their courses. In this paper, the results show that there is a high fault in student responses to the 18 questions and this affects making decisions by depending on it. The students feedback has been collected online in the Covid-19 period in 2020 without taking them into an account the four interlinked features below which are proposed by David Carless as a framework to support students feedback: 'Appreciating Feedback'; 'Making Judgments'; 'Managing Affect'; and 'Taking Action' (Carless et al., 2018b), and all are concluded as follow:

Appreciating Feedback: refers to both the value of the feedback and students' roles. The feedback rating indicates the students' awareness of the value of feedback and an understanding of their active role in the processes. Students have different concepts about feedback and it is often not particularly complex, focusing primarily on feedback as informative.(McLean et al., 2015).

Making Judgments: to gain overall the feedback processes, students need to develop evaluative judgments: the ability to make decisions about the quality of an individual and others' work.(Tai et al., 2016), Underachieving students often have relatively poor self-assessments of their performance and often confuse effort with quality(Boud, Lawson, et al., 2013).

Managing Affects: refer to the feelings, emotions, and situations. Students often show defensive responses to feedback, especially when the feedback is critical or their grades are low.(Robinson et al., 2013).

Taking Action: Feedback requires learners to act on the feedback they have received (Sutton, 2012). Students need to actively engage in understanding the information and using it to inform their later work (Boud & Molloy, 2013).

7. Conclusion

This paper examined the teachers' experiences in e-learning and students feedback reliability on online courses in the Covid-19 era in the DPU. This has been achieved by analyzing feedback of 7709 students in 6 colleges and 8 institutes with 18 questions classified to the different categories such as uploaded resources, availability of e-learning, course organized, student satisfaction on e-learning, Interaction method, experiences on uploaded, students interaction with each other's and student satisfaction on e-learning. Then, our team analyzed 100 courses to respond to the same questions that have been asked to the students for making a comparison with the students' responses. Each question response has values from 1-5 which indicates to the student satisfaction. According to the MHE-KRG criteria, a student's response to 1 or 2 labeled as 'Dissatisfied' and 3, 4 or 5 is labeled 'Satisfied'. The results of the satisfaction of the students' after answering 18 questions and reviewed courses are totally different. It appeared that the students' responses were not reliable enough to depend on it. Therefore, 65.08% students were 'Dissatisfied' with the e-learning while 34.92% were 'Satisfied'. These percentages were far away from the percentages of the analyzing courses. It was 26% 'Dissatisfied' and 74% 'Satisfied' and these percentages showed that the majority of the DPU teachers have the ability to teach students online without any problem. This huge difference occurred because of some reasons according to David Carless, the first reason is taking students feedback as an important learning process evaluation. Secondly, making decisions according to the students' results. Thirdly, collecting students' feedback must be in an appropriate period and it is important to be before the final examination in order to be more accurate. The final reason is the students must see the changes that would happen after collecting their feedbacks.

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